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ABSTRACTS

Characterization of high-strength medium manganese zinc-coated steels for the automotive industry

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B1_7 - Medium Mn Steels & Processing, Andalucía II Room (Level +1), septiembre 16, 2025, 17:00 - 19:00

Advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) continue to evolve in response to the automotive industry's stringent requirements for enhanced environmental sustainability and passenger safety. Within this evolution, medium manganese steels (MMnS), representative of the third generation AHSS, have emerged as exceptional candidates. These steels are characterized by a distinctive compositional range of 3-12 wt.% manganese, up to 0.4 wt.% carbon, complemented by strategic additions of Si, Al, Cr, and microalloying elements (Nb, Ti, and V). Their complex microstructure, comprising ferrite/martensite and retained austenite (>10%), can yield an exceptional combination of high ultimate tensile strength (UTS ~ 1.2-1.6 GPa) and substantial total elongation (TE ~ 15-20%), rendering them particularly suitable for automotive anti-intrusion components and high-energy absorption applications. Moreover, their elevated manganese content facilitates reduced forming temperatures during warm stamping processes while maintaining compatibility with zinc-based corrosion protection coatings, thus addressing historical challenges of liquid metal embrittlement with Zn-coating and associated cracking. This research focused on developing novel medium manganese steels specifically engineered to meet demanding requirements for high-energy absorption (Total Elongation \geq 18%, Ultimate Tensile Strength \geq 1200 MPa) and anti-intrusion (TE \geq 10%, UTS \geq 1500 MPa) components. The alloy design methodology incorporated comprehensive thermodynamic calculations to determine critical transformation temperatures (Ac1, Ac3, Ms) and phase evolution characteristics (volume fraction and chemical composition), using 22MnB5 steel as a benchmark. Based on these calculations, nine distinct steel compositions were formulated varying C, Mn, Al, Cr and B contents, and subsequently produced as 50 kg ingots and processed through sequential hot and cold rolling. The specimens underwent systematic industrial process simulation, encompassing intercritical annealing (700-760°C), hot-dip galvanizing (470°C), hot stamping (700-750°C), and paint baking treatments (170°C, 20 minutes). Through micro-tensile testing, two optimal compositions were identified and subjected to a comprehensive characterization utilizing high-resolution dilatometry, scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction analysis, and hardness measurements. The resultant microstructure consisted of a mixture of ferrite, martensite, and carbon-enriched retained austenite (7-30%), and sometime carbides. The developed materials demonstrated superior mechanical properties, with hardness values ranging from 400 to 500 HV, ultimate tensile strength of 1200-1700 MPa, and total elongation of 10-22%.

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